

Malon-*o*-anisidic Acid and Some of its Derivatives

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Malon-*o*-anisidic acid, its ethyl ester, amide, and hydrazide have been prepared. Malon-*o*-anisidic acid has been condensed with benzaldehyde to yield benzylidene-malon-*o*-anisidic acid and cinnam-*o*-anisidide, with 2-thiophenylaldehyde to yield 2-thienal-malon-*o*-anisidic acid and 2-thienyl-acryl-*o*-anisidide, and with salicylaldehyde, to yield coumarin-3-carboxy-*o*-anisidide. Preparations of malon-*o*-anisidic acid hydrazones of a number of aldehydes and ketones are also reported.

Several derivatives of malonic acid have been prepared by the action of malonic ester on many primary aromatic amines, e.g., malonanilic acid, the three malontoluidic acids¹, the three chloroanilic acids², malon-*p*-iodoanilic acid³, malon-3,4-xylidic acid⁴, malon-*p*-bromoanilic acid⁵, and malon-2,5-xylidic acid⁶. Presence of the reactive methylene group in these acids has been found to be of considerable use in synthetic organic chemistry. The ester, amide, and hydrazide of the above acids are also of some practical importance.

This communication deals with the preparation of malon-*o*-anisidic acid, its ethyl ester, amide, and its hydrazide. The malon-di-*o*-anisidide was obtained as a byproduct during preparation of the above acid. The acid was condensed with benzaldehyde, 2-thiophenylaldehyde, and salicylaldehyde in presence of different condensing agents. Further, from malon-*o*-anisidic acid hydrazide, the hydrazones of benzaldehyde, *o*-chloro-, *o*-nitro- and *o*-methoxy-benzaldehydes, salicylaldehyde, 5-chloro- and 5-bromo-salicylaldehydes, 2-thiophenylaldehyde, furfuraldehyde, chloral, acetone, ethyl methyl ketone, acetophenone, and benzophenone were prepared in good yields, thereby proving the use of the hydrazide in the detection of carbonyl compounds.

EXPERIMENTAL

*Malon-*o*-anisidic Acid (A) and Malon-di-*o*-anisidide (B)*

A mixture of freshly distilled *o*-anisidine (12.3 g., 1*M*) and ethyl malonate (24 g., 1.5*M*) was gently refluxed for 50 min, allowing the alcohol formed to escape and ethyl malonate to flow back. After cooling, ethanol (50 ml) was added and the crystals of malon-di-*o*-anisidide (B) separating were filtered and recrystallised from ethanol; yield 6 g. (18%), m.p. 162°. (Found: N, 8.51. C₁₇H₁₈O₄N₂ requires N, 8.90%).

1. Chattaway and Olmsted, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1910, 97, 938.
2. George and Ittyerah, *Agra Univ. J. Res. (Sci)*, 1955, 4, 299.
3. Athana and Ittyerah, *ibid.*, 1963, 12, Part II, 81.
4. Chellapa and Ittyerah, *this Journal*, 1953, 30, 387.
5. Phillip P. Benjamin, M. Sc. Thesis, Agra University, 1955.
6. Phillip and Ittyerah, *Indian J. Appl. Chem.*, 1963, 26, 168.

The filtrate was mixed with sodium carbonate (10 g.), dissolved in water (25 ml), and steam was blown through it for an hour. The solution on cooling deposited a little more of the di-anisidide. This was filtered and the clear solution was acidified with HCl (conc.). Malon-*o*-anisidic acid was obtained as a white crystalline precipitate (yield 14 g., 67%). It was recrystallised from water or aqueous ethanol, m.p. 150° (decomp.). (Found: N, 6.53. $C_{10}H_{11}O_4N$ requires N, 6.60%).

The effect of variation in duration of heating and in the molecular proportion of the amine and the ester on the yield of the acid was studied. The conditions mentioned above were found optimum.

Ethyl Malon-o-anisidate (C).—In another experiment, after refluxing the mixture of *o*-anisidine and ethyl malonate and removing the di-anisidide as described before, the ethanolic extract was concentrated on a steam bath to half the volume. The sticky product obtained on cooling was crystallised from petroleum (b.p. 55-80°) in colorless prisms, yield 3.5 g. (29%), m.p. 65°. (Found: N, 6.1. $C_{12}H_{15}O_4N$ requires N, 5.9%).

Malon-o-anisidamide (D) was prepared by dissolving the ester (C) (2 g.) in ethanol (15 ml) and then adding the solution slowly with stirring to liquor ammonia (50 ml). The mixture was kept for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. and the crystals of the amide formed were filtered and recrystallised from aqueous ethanol; yield 1.5 g., m.p. 159°. (Found: N, 13.0. $C_{10}H_{12}O_3N_2$ requires N, 13.4%).

Malon-o-anisidic Acid Hydrazide (E).—Hydrazine hydrate (5 ml, 70%) was added to ethyl malon-*o*-anisidate (C) (2 g.), dissolved in ethanol (20 ml). Heat was evolved and within 30 min. crystals of the acid hydrazide separated. These were filtered and recrystallised from aqueous ethanol, yield 1.4 g., m.p. 109°. (Found: N, 18.54. $C_{10}H_{13}O_3N_3$ requires N, 18.8%).

Benzylidene-malon-o-anisidic Acid and Cinnam-o-anisidide.—Malon-*o*-anisidic acid (2 g.) and benzaldehyde (1 g.) were mixed and heated at 105° for 4 hr. The contents were then extracted with a warm solution of sodium bicarbonate in which the entire mass dissolved. The alkali extract on addition of excess of HCl (conc.) and on keeping in ice water deposited benzylidene-malon-*o*-anisidic acid (1.4 g., 47%). When recrystallised from aqueous ethanol it melted at 146° (decomp.). (Found: N, 4.96. $C_{17}H_{15}O_4N$ requires N, 4.71%).

The above experiment was repeated using a trace of pyridine (0.1 ml) as condensing agent. On extraction with sodium bicarbonate solution, a residue was left, which on crystallisation from aqueous ethanol afforded 1.52 g. (60%) of cinnam-*o*-anisidide, m.p. 116°. (Found: N, 5.32. $C_{16}H_{13}O_4N$ requires N, 5.53%).

2-Thenal-malon-o-anisidic Acid and 2-Thienyl-acryl-o-anisidide.—A mixture of malon-*o*-anisidic acid (1.5 g.), 2-thiophenylaldehyde (0.85 g.), and a drop of pyridine was heated for 4 hr. at 105°. The resulting mass on extraction with sodium bicarbonate solution left a residue, which on recrystallisation from aqueous ethanol melted at 80°. This was identified as 2-thienyl-acryl-*o*-anisidide, yield 0.6 g. (31%). (Found: N, 5.6. $C_{14}H_{13}O_4NS$ requires N, 5.4%). The alkali extract on addition of HCl (conc.) deposited 2-thenal-malon-*o*-anisidic acid (1 g., 44%) which after recrystallisation from aqueous ethanol melted at 189° (decomp.). (Found: N, 4.96. $C_{13}H_{13}O_4NS$ requires N, 4.62%).

Coumarin-3-carboxy-o-anisidide.—Malon-*o*-anisidic acid (1.04 g.), salicylaldehyde (0.6 g.), and a drop of pyridine were heated at 105° for 4 hr. The yellow mass obtained was washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and the residue extracted with hot ethanol (20 ml). The insoluble product, coumarin-3-carboxy-*o*-anisidide (0.46 g., 31%), was recrystallised from glacial acetic acid, m.p. 240°. (Found: N, 4.71. C₁₇H₁₃O₄N requires N, 4.70%).

Malon o-anisidic Acid Hydrazones (General Method).—Equimolecular quantities of the acid hydrazide (E) and the carbonyl compound, both dissolved in minimum quantity of ethanol, were warmed and kept aside for a few minutes, when the hydrazone crystallised; with ketones the mixture had to be refluxed for 2 hr. and cooled overnight. In some cases like chloral, furfuraldehyde, 2-thiophenylaldehyde, the formation of the hydrazones took a longer time. Table I records different hydrazones obtained, their yields, m.p. etc.

TABLE I

Malon- <i>o</i> -anisidic acid hydrazone of	Formula.	M.P.	Yield.	Found.	Reqd.
Benzaldehyde	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ O ₃ N ₃	164°	65%	N : 13.37%	13.50%
<i>o</i> -Chlorobenzaldehyde	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ O ₃ N ₃ Cl	198°	100	Cl : 10.33	10.27
<i>o</i> -Nitrobenzaldehyde	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ O ₅ N ₄	187°	30	N : 15.91	15.73
<i>o</i> -Methoxybenzaldehyde	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ O ₄ N ₃	200°	100	N : 12.27	12.31
Salicylaldehyde	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ O ₄ N ₃	178°	100	N : 12.76	12.84
5-Chlorosalicylaldehyde	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ O ₄ N ₃ Cl	217°	70	Cl : 9.68	9.82
5-Bromosalicylaldehyde	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ O ₄ N ₃ Br	222°	80	Br : 19.41	19.70
2-Thiophenylaldehyde	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ O ₃ N ₃ S	147°	60	S : 10.19	10.09
Furfuraldehyde	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ O ₄ N ₃	141°	60	N : 13.84	13.95
Chloral hydrate	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ O ₃ N ₃ Cl ₃	152°	80	Cl : 29.57	30.21
Acetone	C ₁₃ H ₁₇ O ₃ N ₃	126°	48	N : 15.90	16.00
Ethyl methyl ketone	C ₁₄ H ₁₉ O ₃ N ₃	120°	60	N : 14.86	15.16
Acetophenone	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ O ₃ N ₃	173°	30	N : 12.85	12.92
Benzophenone	C ₂₃ H ₂₁ O ₃ N ₃	102°	40	N : 10.09	10.85

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